

PREPARATION OF WOMEN WITH GLOMERULONEPHRITIS FOR PREGNANCY

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Suyarkulova Madhiya Erkinovna

*FJSTI Department of Traumatology, Obstetrics and
Gynecology, Candidate of Medical Sciences Phd*

Abdullaeva Muazzam Rustamjon kizi

FJSTI Obstetrics and Gynecology,

1st year master's degree

Fergana, Uzbekistan

Annotation: *The problem of kidney disease is relevant among pregnant women because it is the leading pathology among pregnant women and poses a serious risk to the pregnancy process and normal development of the fetus, as the pathology of these organs leads to disorders. many vital functions of the body and pregnancy significantly increase the load on the kidneys. Increased demands on the kidneys and neurohumoral changes specific to the period of pregnancy help to identify congenital or acquired defects, latent diseases of the urinary system. Kidney diseases are prone to the development of late toxicosis in pregnant women, the main manifestations of which (hypertension, proteinuria, edema) are associated with impaired nephron function.*

Keywords: *kidney disease, toxicosis, glomerulonephritis, blood pressure, side effects, chronic glomerulonephritis.*

INTRODUCTION. A rare but very dangerous disease of the kidneys is glomerulonephritis - an immunoinflammatory disease of the kidneys, characterized by damage to the glomeruli or renal glomeruli.

The clinical manifestations of the disease depend on its severity and form. Sometimes it is just a manifestation of urinary syndrome - the detection of large amounts of protein, red blood cells and other pathological elements (cylinders) in the urine. In severe cases, the symptoms of the disease are manifested by renal failure, an increase in blood pressure, which adversely affects the condition of the patient and the fetus. [1]

Most pregnant women with glomerulonephritis develop various pregnancy complications. They are more likely to develop preeclampsia, placental insufficiency, anemia and kidney failure. Impaired renal function is a prognosis of fetal loss and premature birth. Diagnosis of glomerulonephritis is based on

urine tests, assessment of the presence of arterial hypertension and the presence of renal failure. [8]

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

In 20-30% of patients with chronic glomerulonephritis, this is the result of acute glomerulonephritis, the causative agent of which may be streptococci (especially group A hemolytic streptococci, strains 1, 3, 4, 12, 18), staphylococci, adenovirus, rhinovirus infections, mycoplasmas, hepatitis B virus. drugs, vaccines, serums, organic solvents, alcohol, etc. [1,2]

The pathogenesis of chronic glomerulonephritis during pregnancy consists of the formation of an immunocomplex process, the components of which are the corresponding antigens, antibodies and complement factor C3. The level of phagocytic reactivity of the organism, the quality of the antigen, the quantitative ratio between antigens and antibodies determine the quantitative and qualitative characteristics of immune complexes formed in the circulatory bed and fixed subendothelially, subepithelially in the renal glomeruli, can be formed in the intramembrane form, in the mesangium, and directly in the glomerular structures. The deposition of immune complexes initiates a cascade of biochemical cellular reactions that result in the formation of cytokines, the migration of polymorphonuclear leukocytes, monocytes, eosinophils, and the activation of intracellular proteolytic enzymes. [3]

RESULTS. The onset of glomerular nephritis in pregnant women is triggered by the same factors as those outside of pregnancy. The inflammatory-atrophic process in the renal glomeruli is often the result of infection, but in some patients it is caused by other conditions that accompany the formation of immune complexes. Sometimes the etiology of glomerulonephritis remains unknown. The causes of the disease during pregnancy can be as follows.

The development of acute cyclic glomerulonephritis detected in pregnant women is confirmed by complaints of weakness, pain in the lower back, headache, worsening or loss of appetite, fever 38 ° C and above, chills. Urination is significantly reduced or completely stopped. There is swelling of the face and eyelids. Urine is frothy, pink, red or brown. It is possible for the patient to increase blood pressure relative to normal levels. Symptoms of acute glomerulonephritis usually appear within 1–3 weeks after infection. [7]

In 60-63% of pregnant women, glomerular inflammation is chronic, asymptomatic, and detected only in laboratory studies. In the hematuric form, a darkening of the urine or the appearance of blood in it is usually observed. In 7% of women, a hypertensive variant is diagnosed - general weakness, periodic headaches, dizziness, increased blood pressure with complaints of noise in the ears. In 5% of cases, glomerulonephritis persists with severe swelling of the face (especially in the morning) and limbs on the nephrotic variant. In severe

cases, general edema (anasarca), ascites, hydrothorax are detected, a significant increase in abdominal volume, shortness of breath, fatigue, weakness. The appearance of hypertensive and nephrotic forms in approximately 25% of patients is combined with a decrease in the severity of symptoms compared to isolated variants of the disease. [9]

DISCUSSION. Acute glomerulonephritis during pregnancy is often undiagnosed and is considered severe preeclampsia. The onset of preeclampsia before 28 weeks of gestation, the appearance of hematuria, and the detection of high titers of antistreptolysin and antigialuronidase are indicative of acute glomerulonephritis. The clinical signs of chronic glomerulonephritis during pregnancy depend on the variant, stage, and stage of the disease. Often clinical forms of chronic glomerulonephritis are observed, which are characterized by mild proteinuria, erythrocyturia without arterial hypertension. We are talking about chronic glomerulonephritis with urinary syndrome and prehypertensive stage (latent form). The addition of arterial hypertension indicates sclerotic processes in the kidneys (hypertensive stage glomerulonephritis). The specific form of the disease indicates the activity of this process glomerulonephritis with nephrotic syndrome - the presence of tumors, proteinuria greater than 3 g / day, hypodysproteinemia, hyperlipidemia, hypercoagulability of the blood. The next stage of the disease is chronic renal failure, which is manifested by increased levels of urea and creatinine in the blood, anemia, decreased ability of the kidneys to concentrate, arterial hypertension and degenerative changes in other organs. It is believed that pregnancy does not occur if the level of creatinine in the blood plasma is higher than 0.3 mmol / l. The next stage of the disease is chronic renal failure, which is manifested by increased levels of urea and creatinine in the blood, anemia, decreased ability of the kidneys to concentrate, arterial hypertension and degenerative changes in other organs. It is believed that pregnancy does not occur if the level of creatinine in the blood plasma is higher than 0.3 mmol / l. The next stage of the disease is chronic renal failure, which is manifested by increased levels of urea and creatinine in the blood, anemia, decreased ability of the kidneys to concentrate, arterial hypertension and degenerative changes in other organs. It is believed that pregnancy does not occur if the level of creatinine in the blood plasma is higher than 0.3 mmol / l. [4,5]

Most pregnant women complain of:

- swelling of the face, especially in the morning;
- pain in the lumbar region;
- headache and weakness;
- weak urination until there is no urine;
- significant increase in blood pressure;

- increase in body temperature. [6]

CONCLUSION

It is difficult to adequately assess the physical condition of a pregnant woman, so the only way to detect pathological changes in the body is to examine the urine under a microscope. A characteristic feature of the disease is an increase in the total density of urine due to the high number of different cells, as well as a decrease in transparency and protein loss.

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